

ORGANO ARSENICALS AS POSSIBLE FILARICIDES

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Some 1 : 4-di-substituted piperazine derivatives containing pentavalent arsenic have been prepared as possible filaricides.

In recent years some 1 : 4-di-substituted piperazines (Hewett *et al.*, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1947, **32**, 1293) have been found to possess filaricidal properties. Hetrazan, which is 1-diethylcarbamyl-4-methylpiperazine, has been found to be the most active of all the compounds so far investigated (Santiago-Stevenson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Med. Assoc.*, 1947, **135**, 708, ; Harned *et al.*, *J. Lab. Clin. Med.*, 1948, **33**, 216). It decreases the microfilariae in patients very rapidly but the adult worms are not rapidly killed. Though this drug kills all the microfilariae in patients quickly, yet its clinical results in patients do not appear to be very conclusive.

Arsenical compounds, which are known to have a definite beneficial effect on filaria (cf. Chopra and Sunder Rao, *Indian Med. Gaz.*, 1929, **64**, 130; *Indian J. Med. Res.*, 1939, **27**, 549) cannot, however, kill the microfilariae appreciably, but kill the adult worms (Rose and Culbertson, *J. Parasitol.*, 1945, **31**, suppl. 6, 17 ; Otto and Maren, *Science*, 1947, **106**, 105).

In view of the above observations, some 1 : 4-di-substituted piperazines containing arsenic have now been prepared with the object of pharmacological examination against filaria.

1 : 4-*p*-Diaminodiphenylpiperazine (Morley, *Ber.*, 1880, **13**, 1793) has now been subjected to Bart's reaction to yield the arsonic acid derivative (I).

Piperazine and its mono-substituted derivatives have been reacted with sodium salt of 4-chloroacetylaminophenylarsonic acid (Jacobs and Heidelberger, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1919, **41**, 1810) to produce the arsonic acid derivatives, (II) and (III) respectively.

These pentavalent arsonic acids have been readily reduced to trivalent arsenoxides by PCl_3 in an inert medium, like ethyl acetate, and subsequent treatment with dilute alkali.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

1: 4-Di-(*phenyl-p-arsonic acid*)-piperazine (I).—1: 4-*p*-Diaminodiphenylpiperazine (3 g.), dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid (45 c.c. of 1.5*N*), was diazotised with sodium nitrite (2.6 g.) under cooling. The diazotised solution was gradually added with stirring to a solution prepared by dissolving As_2O_3 (3.8 g.), Na_2CO_3 (7.5 g.), $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 5\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.4 g.) and NaOH (1.5 g.) in water (50 c.c.) to which sufficient liquor ammonia was added to get a clear solution. Next day the solution was filtered, the filtrate partly concentrated, and the clear solution was made acidic with dilute acetic acid, when a brown substance separated out. This solid after filtration was again dissolved in NaHCO_3 and the arsonic acid was reprecipitated from the clear solution by dilute acetic acid. It is a light brown solid (1.6 g.) which could not be crystallised from common solvents. It does not melt at 280° . (Found: N, 5.1; As, 29.9. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{N}_2\text{As}_2$ requires N, 5.76; As, 30.86 per cent.) It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids.

Piperazine-1: 4-di-(*acetanilide-p-arsonic acid*), $\text{H}_2\text{O}_2\text{AsC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NH} \cdot \text{COCH}_2 \cdot \text{NC}_6\text{H}_5\text{N} \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{CONH} \cdot \text{C}_6\text{H}_4\text{AsO}_3\text{H}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (II).—A mixture of piperazine hexahydrate (2 g.), 4-chloroacetylaminophenylarsonic acid (7 g.), sodium carbonate (1.2 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) and water (80 c.c.) was refluxed for 2 hours, when a solid separated out. This was cooled, acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid, and the white solid after boiling with water was filtered. This solid was again dissolved in sodium carbonate solution and acidified with acetic acid when the substance separated out. It does not melt even at 280° ; it cannot be crystallised from any common solvent and it contains two molecules of water of crystallisation. (Found: N, 9.5; As, 22.9. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{As}_2$ requires N, 9.3; As, 25.0. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{As}_2$ requires N, 8.8; As 23.59 per cent.) The compound on drying over P_2O_5 at 105° for 6 hours under vacuum loses 2 molecules of water and this anhydrous compound on analysis gave 24.5% As.

1: 4-Di-*N*-(*phenyl-p-arsonic acid*)-aminoacetyl piperazine ($\text{H}_2\text{O}_2\text{AsC}_6\text{H}_4\text{NHCH}_2 \cdot \text{CONC}_6\text{H}_5\text{NCO} \cdot \text{CH}_2\text{NHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{AsO}_3\text{H}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) was obtained from 1: 4 dichloroacetyl piperazine (Abderhalden and Rossner, *Z. physiol. Chem.*, 1925, 144, 219) and sodium salt of *p*-arsanilic acid in the similar manner as have been described above. It does not melt even at 280° and its properties are the same as its isomer. (Found: N, 9.2; As, 22.81. $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_4\text{As}_2$ requires N, 8.8; As, 23.59 per cent.)

Piperazine-carbethoxy-4-acetanilide-*p*-arsonic acid ($\text{EtOCONC}_6\text{H}_5\text{NCH}_2\text{CONHC}_6\text{H}_4\text{AsO}_3\text{H}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) (III, $\text{R}=\text{CO}_2\text{Et}$) was prepared from *N*-monocarbethoxypiperazine (Moore *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1929, 39) and 4-chloroacetylaminophenylarsonic acid. It is soluble in dilute mineral acids and can be crystallised from hot water or dilute alcohol. It melts with frothing at 210° , and contains 2 molecules of water of crystallisation. (Found: N, 8.8; As 16.4. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8\text{N}_4\text{As}$ requires N, 9.32; As, 16.63 per cent.)

1: 4-Di-(*phenyl-p-arsenoxide*)-piperazine.—The corresponding arsonic acid (2 g.) was suspended in 20 c.c. of dry ethyl acetate and 2 c.c. of PCl_3 gradually added to it under shaking. After standing for half an hour the mixture was warmed on a water-bath for 5 minutes when HCl gas was evolved. On cooling, ice-cold water was added, made alkaline with dilute sodium hydroxide, the water layer twice shaken with ether, and the arsenoxide was precipitated with ammonium chloride. It is a brown solid

insoluble in dilute acids and cannot be crystallised from any common solvent; it shrinks at 240° and melts at 270° to a brown viscous liquid. (Found: N, 6.3; As, 34.9. $C_{16}H_{16}O_2N_2As$, requires N, 6.69; As, 35.88 per cent).

Piperazine-1: 4-di (acetanilide-p-arsenoxide) (OAs. $C_6H_4NHCOCH_2NC_6H_4N$. CH_2CONH . C_6H_4AsO . $2H_2O$) was prepared from the corresponding arsonic acid by PCl_3 . It is insoluble in hot water, soluble to some extent in hot dilute alcohol, and does not melt even at 280° . (Found: As, 25.8. $C_{20}H_{20}O_6N_4As_2$ requires As, 26.4 per cent).

1: 4-Di-N-(phenyl-p-arsenoxide)-aminoacetyl piperazine (OAs $C_6H_4NHCH_2CO$. N . C_6H_4N . $COCH_2NH$. O_6H_4AsO . $2H_2O$).—The method of preparation and properties are same as in the previous compound.

Piperazine-1-carbethoxy-4-acetanilide-p-arsenoxide (EtOCONC $_6$ H $_4$ NCH $_2$ CONH-C $_6$ H $_4$ AsO. $2H_2O$) was prepared from the corresponding arsonic acid with PCl_3 . This compound is soluble in hot water and dilute alcohol. It shrinks and softens to a glassy mass at 92° and decomposes with frothing at 120° . (Found: As, 18.5. $C_{13}H_{14}O_6N_2As$ requires As, 17.99 per cent).

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